

Studies on New Mesogens. Part-I.

p-(*p*'-*n*-Alkoxy-cinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-*p*"-*n*-propoxyanilines

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A new homologous series *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-*p*"-*n*-propoxyanilines has been synthesised and its mesomorphic characteristics have been studied. It is a high melting series and exhibits rich mesomorphism. The range over which mesomorphic order prevails varies between 86° to 150°. The nematic isotropic transition curve shows odd-even effect. Polymesomorphism is also exhibited by the series, beginning from the seventh homologue with the appearance of smectic mesophase at about 125°. The S-N transition curve rises in a smooth fashion enhancing the smectic mesophase range at the cost of nematic mesophase length. Extrapolation of the smectic-nematic transition curve to the left, in keeping with its smoothness, makes it possible to determine the latent transition temperatures. The nematic mesophase shows a threaded texture while the smectic mesophase exhibits a focal conic fan-shaped smectic 'A' texture.

In this investigation a new homologous series of mesogens has been synthesised and its mesomorphic characteristics have been determined.

Experimental

The following compounds required for the synthesis of the new homologous series were synthesised by the methods described in literature: *p*-*n*-alkoxybenzaldehydes¹, *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids², *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyl chlorides³, *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzaldehydes⁴, and *p*-*n*-propoxyaniline⁵.

p-(*p*'-*n*-Alkoxy-cinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-*p*"-*n*-propoxyanilines: Equimolar amount (0.01 mol) of the corresponding *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzaldehyde and *p*-*n*-propoxyaniline in ethanol (20 ml) containing a few drops of acetic acid was refluxed for 1 h. For higher members, the refluxing period was extended to ~3 h. The products were crystallised from benzene-ethanol (20:80) mixture. The Schiff's base obtained were almost white or pale yellow. The transition temperatures are compiled in Table 1. The elemental analyses were found satisfactory.

Results and Discussion

p-(*p*'-*n*-Alkoxy-cinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-*p*"-*n*-propoxyanilines is a very high melting homologous series. Mesomorphism exhibited by this series which with three benzene rings would possess high aromaticity, is quite rich, the temperature range being 86-150°. A plot of alkyl chain length vs the transition temperatures (Fig. 1) gives an interesting reading.

TABLE 1—*p*-(*p*'-*n*-ALKOXYCINNAMOVLOXY)BENZYLIDENE-*p*"-*n*-PROPOXYANILINES

n-Alkyl group	Transition temp (°C)		Isotropic
	Smectic	Nematic	
Methyl	—	140	290
Ethyl	—	155	293
Propyl	—	148	278
Butyl	—	140	277
Pentyl	—	125	266
Hexyl	(105) ^a	128	262
Heptyl	125	135	252
Octyl	116	155	250
Decyl	120	175	235
Dodecyl	130	185	225
Tetradecyl	118	198	215
Octadecyl	105	175	192

^aValue in parenthesis indicates monotropy and is obtained by extrapolation.

The solid-mesomorphic curve follows a zig-zag rising and falling pattern. The nematic-isotropic transition curves show a continuous falling tendency, simultaneously displaying odd-even effect upto the eighth homologue. The alternation effect seems to peter off after the eighth homologue, while the nematic property is exhibited upto the octadecyl homologue. Polymesomorphism is exhibited by the series from the seventh homologue as smectic mesophase makes its appearance at about 125°. The smectic-nematic transition curve rises in a smooth arch like manner decreasing the nematic mesophase range. The smectic property attains maximum at the tetradecyloxy homologue. The curve falls thereafter, but since fall in the nematic-isotropic curve is greater than that of the smectic-nematic curve, the narrowing of the nematic mesophase range continues unabated up to the end. Extrapolation of the smectic-nematic curve to the left in

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Fig. 1. Plots of alkyl chain length vs transition temperature of p -(p' - n -alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene- p'' - n -propoxyanilines: (---) solid mesomorph, (Δ) smectic-nematic, and ($\circ$) nematic-isotropic.

keeping with its smoothness makes it possible to determine the latent transition temperature for the smectic mesophase for the hexyloxy homologue which is 105° though its extremely steep nature makes it difficult to yield reliable extrapolate values for the fifth and lower homologues.

The nematic mesophase, as observed under polarising microscope, shows a threaded texture while the smectic mesophase shows a focal conic fan-shaped smectic 'A' texture.

The present homologous series has been compared for thermal stabilities and other characteristics with other homologous series (Chart 1), namely,

p -(p' - n -Alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene- p'' -anisidines (J)^a

p -(p' - n -Alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene- p'' -phenetidines (G)^a

p -(p' - n -Alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene- p'' - n -propoxyanilines (D-I)

Chart 1. Homologous series under comparison.

p -(p' - n -alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene- p'' -anisidines⁶ (J) and p -(p' - n -alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene- p'' -phenetidines⁷ (G). These series differ from the present series at their right terminals (with lesser number of carbon atoms) with all other molecular characteristics remaining the same.

It is observed that J and G series under reference exhibit wider nematic mesomorphic range than the present series D-I. These series J and G at the same time exhibit a little bit lesser smectic mesophase ranges. If J, G and D-I series are taken in sequence of their right terminal substituents OCH_3 , OC_2H_5 , and OC_3H_7 , respectively, then the indication for the decreasing nematic character and increasing smectic character for the series as the alkyl chain length of the terminal substituents increases is well discerned.

The nematic order will be $\text{OCH}_3 > \text{OC}_2\text{H}_5 > \text{OC}_3\text{H}_7$, while the smectic order will just be the reversed one. The odd-even effect becomes progressively prominent, rather from almost 'absence' to 'prominence' in the sequence of increasing alkyl chain length of the right terminal substituent of the homologues of series under discussion.

Thermal stabilities of the present homologous series has also been compared with other homologous series. The calculated values of average thermal stabilities are given (Table 2). The nematic-isotropic thermal stabilities of these three series are quite high. The highest one is for G series. It is observed that as the CH_2 units are added at the right terminal alkyl chain, i.e. as the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain increases, the nematic-isotropic thermal stability decreases. With increasing polarisability of the molecules, the nematic-isotropic stability would be decreasing since polarisability is not the singularly exclusive factor, but the end-to-end adhesions have more than any other factors to contribute to the nematic orientation. Highly polar end-groups will cause greater end-to-end adhesions; the OC_2H_5 group of the G series under reference is highly polar which gives rise to high end-to-end adhesion. Any further addition of CH_2 units will not be enhancing polarity of the molecules, but the overall polarisability of the molecules will be greatly affected giving rise to large variation in molecular forces.

TABLE 2—AVERAGE THERMAL STABILITIES ($^\circ\text{C}$)

	Series		
	J	G	D-I
Nematic - Isotropic	270	281.3	254.6
Smectic - Nematic	$\text{C}_6 - \text{C}_6$	$\text{C}_6 - \text{C}_6$	$\text{C}_6 - \text{C}_6$
Smectic - Isotropic	167.2	178.6	182.6
Commencement of smectic phase	$\text{C}_{12} - \text{C}_{12}$	$\text{C}_{12} - \text{C}_{12}$	$\text{C}_{12} - \text{C}_{12}$
	C_6	C_6	C_7 (C_6) ^a

^aValue in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

The more significant fact is the alternation of the nematic-isotropic stabilities of the three series,

viz. J, G and D-I. The series J and D-I having odd number of carbon at their right terminal alkyl chain (*i.e.* one and three, respectively) show low thermal stability than the series G having even number, (*i.e.* two carbon at its right terminal alkyl chain). The homologous series J, G and D-I have a sequence of increasing smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic thermal stabilities as the alkyl chain length increases at the right terminals due to increase in polarisability.

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